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ABSTRACT:

The paper presents research on robot's command recognition and motion capture. There is developed a command system, which is pre-defined and universal for the motion of a great amount of robots. The system perceives all commands given by the operator as a three-dimensional vector of values. In the process of experiments using machine learning methods, research and classification of signals for each of the commands and states of the robot based on the data received from the sensors was performed. For machine learning of the system, it was decided to use the MatLab program package

Key words: Mobile Robot, Control Command, Command Recognition, Robot Control System, Manufacturing Innovation, Industrial Innovation.

INTRODUCTION

Today, robotics is an integral part of all spheres of human activity and everyday life: millions of robots work in manufacturing and service enterprises; underwater manipulators are used in research and rescue work; robots and manipulators are widely used in space research [1]-[15]. The most demanded is the use of robots and robotic systems to perform difficult, harmful, tiring and monotonous work [16]-[18].

Modern mobile robots are able to independently explore the environment, solve a set of tasks provided by the developers. However, in some applications, this does not guarantee their complete autonomy. Incomplete determination of technological situations, random external influences, insufficient information about the state of the environment require constant identification of the states of the robot and the environment, for which intelligent control algorithms are used [19]-[26]. Various methods and approaches can also be used here [27]-[38].

Modern mobile robot control systems are divided into three types: automatic, biotechnical and interactive. The use of automatic control systems is impossible in the case of incomplete certainty of technological situations, so biotechnical and interactive types have gained popularity. The biotechnical type of control allows a person to gain full control over a robotic system [39]-[41]. The interactive type allows for combined control of the system, both in automatic mode and human control. When using a biotechnical or interactive type of control, there is a need to set up human-machine communication. For this, command recognition systems are used.

Command recognition systems are an integral part of remote control of a mobile robot. Today, command recognition systems that use the principles of: motion capture are popular; visual control; control of levers and buttons; etc. The variety of commands and methods of setting them makes it possible to clearly and unambiguously make the system understand the operator's wishes.

However, the command recognition system based on the principle of motion capture is not well developed in the modern world.

The development of a command recognition system for intelligent control technology of a mobile robot is an urgent scientific task, as there are cases in which a mobile robot cannot make a decision on its own and needs remote control.

Related works

The problem of command recognition and motion capture has become extremely relevant with the advent of new sensors and increasing requirements for the accuracy and speed of positioning of mobile robots. Many scientific works are devoted to its solution, let us consider some of them.

In article [42] authors synthesize and evaluate studies investigating the use of motion capture technologies in industry-related research. They note that motion capture sensors, such as visual cameras and inertial measurement units, are frequently adopted in industrial settings to support solutions in robotics, additive manufacturing, teleworking and human safety.

The study [43] proposes an approach to improve the performance of mobile robot systems for optimal path planning. The technique utilizes motion capture technology to collect real-time data on the robot's movements, generate optimal path planning strategies, and enable remote control and monitoring of the robot's activities.

Scientists in [44] present research on methods of a wheeled mobile robot localization using an optical motion capture system. The results of localization based on the model of forward kinematics and odometric measurements were compared.

The paper [45] proposes a performance evaluation protocol that takes the characters of both optical motion capture and robotic 3C (Computer, Communication, and Consumer Electronics) product assembly operations into account.

The researchers in [46] consider the ball-catching system. It was composed of an omni-directional wheeled mobile robot and an image processing system that included a dynamic stereo vision camera and a static camera, was used to capture a thrown ball. The thrown ball was tracked by the dynamic stereo vision camera, and the omni-directional wheeled mobile robot was navigated through the static camera.

Lighthouse technology, commercially known as SteamVR tracking, is a 3D motion capture system developed for virtual reality applications that couples light-based and inertial tracking methods [47]. Authors [47] benchmark its performance in motion tracking for possible applications in biomechanics and robotics. The tracking performance of the system was evaluated to determine the accuracy and repeatability for pose measurements from dynamic studies.

Command system for movement control development

This study is a continuation of the works [48] and [49].

When developing a control system for a mobile robot, a set of actions for which it is intended or programmed is pre-defined. Since the system being developed must be universal (it can be used for various mobile robots), it makes sense to issue universal commands only for controlling the movement of the robot, since each of the robots has its own specific functionality and its own specific purpose. The set of universal commands includes: move forward, move back, stop, turn right 45°, turn left 45°, turn right 90° and turn left 90°. Each of the operator's commands must be pre-defined and machine-trained for its recognition.

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In order to achieve high accuracy in recognizing the operator's commands, the number of experimental fixations of values from the sensors must be quite large. In machine learning of the system, the accuracy of operator command recognition has a direct dependence on the size of the sample. Since the sensor continuously sends data about the state of the motion capture system, this data must first be filtered.

The proposed system of commands for controlling the movement of a mobile robot has a three-dimensional (three-axis) nature. The system will perceive all commands given by the operator as a three-dimensional vector of values $\vec{a}=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$. At the machine learning stage, each command must be assigned to a certain command class. For example, the forward movement command can be represented as a vector $\vec{a}=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$, and this vector can be specified as following:

$$\vec{a}_1 = [x_n, y_n, z_n], \vec{a}_2 = [x_n, y_n, z_n] \dots \vec{a}_m = [x_n, y_n, z_n]. \tag{1}$$

The system of commands in the form of classes and their corresponding states of the sensors is generally presented in Table 1.

In the control process, the robot must transmit data from the sensor and information about its current state or movement process. This information must undergo a filtering procedure and be recognized by establishing its belonging to the appropriate class of signals corresponding to a particular command. The system of states of a mobile robot in the form of states of sensors and corresponding classes of states of the robot is generally presented in Table 2.

Table 1: Command system in general

Command class	Command in the form of a vector of sensor values
Movement forward	$\vec{a}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{a}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{a}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$
Movement backward	$\vec{b}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{b}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{b}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$
Stop	$\vec{c}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{c}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{c}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$
Left turn 45°	$\vec{d}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{d}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{d}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$
Right turn 45°	$\vec{e}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{e}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{e}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$
Left turn 90°	$\vec{g}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{g}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{g}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$
Right turn 90°	$\vec{h}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{h}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{h}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$

Table 2: Robot state class system in general

The state of the sensors in the form of a vector of values	Robot status class
$\vec{i}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{i}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{i}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$	The robot is moving
$\vec{j}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{j}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{j}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$	The robot is standing
$\vec{k}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{k}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{k}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$	The robot turns left
$\vec{l}_1=[x_1, y_1, z_1], \vec{l}_2=[x_2, y_2, z_2] \dots \vec{l}_m=[x_n, y_n, z_n]$	The robot turns right

In the process of experiments using machine learning methods, research and classification of signals for each of the commands and states of the robot based on the data received from the

sensors was performed. Such training is an iterative experimental process, which includes the following stages:

- system training for operator teams;
- teaching the system to the states of the mobile robot;
- training of the decision-making system.

The basis of these processes are the solving of classification and recognition problems.

Planning experiments with system elements

Commands to the operator can be given in various ways, depending on the control conditions. They can be limited by the sensitivity of the sensor or the conditions of the command task. Therefore, it became necessary to establish the minimum necessary and optimally necessary number of movements of the operator to control the mobile robot with the specified accuracy. According to the specifications, the recognition accuracy should be equal to or at least 98%. From

this it follows that the maximum permissible error of recognition $\hat{\partial}_{n.p.} = 0,02$.

For machine learning of the system, it was decided to use the MatLab program package, as it has all the necessary technical capabilities for this.

The quality of system learning depends on such parameters as:

- study time;
- model training accuracy;
- accuracy of teaching within classes;
- prediction speed.

Also, quality assessment is performed using graphic methods. With the help of the MatLab environment, it is possible to generate: a scatter diagram, an error matrix, an ROC curve and a graph of parallel coordinates.

The error matrix shown in Figure 1 is a special type of contingency table, with two parameters ("actual" and "predicted") and identical sets of "classes" in both dimensions (each combination of dimension and class is a variable in the contingency table).

Figure 1: Example of an error matrix

The error matrix necessary for calculating the values of precision, recall, and F-measure is presented in Figure 2. The parallel coordinates graph is presented in Figure 3.

1komanda	1212	2			6		
2 komanda	30	1336	11		12		
3 komanda	1	20	1094	15			
4 komanda			3	944			
5 komanda	17	24	3		1037		
6 komanda				1	2	1219	56
7 komanda						17	975
	1komanda	2 komanda	3 komanda	4 komanda	5 komanda	6 komanda	7 komanda
	Predicted class						

Figure 2: Error matrix

Figure 3: Parallel coordinates graph

CONCLUSION

The analysis of ROC curves showed that command № 7 has the smallest AUC area of 0.96, which significantly worsens the recognition accuracy indicator. On the graph of parallel coordinates, there is a clear dash-dotted line of false recognition of command №7, which shows the need to replace it with another command or re-form the training sample with a more accurate submission by the operator of this command to achieve higher recognition accuracy.

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